

SURVIVAL OUTCOMES AND RELATED FACTORS IN ELDERLY PATIENTS WITH LUNG CANCER

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Keywords

Lung cancer

Elderly

Survival rate

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ABSTRACT

This retrospective cohort study aimed to evaluate five-year overall survival and key prognostic factors among elderly patients diagnosed with lung cancer. The study included all individuals aged ≥ 65 years who were diagnosed with lung cancer in Sivas province between 2013 and 2017 and who had completed at least five years of follow-up. Survival outcomes were estimated using the Kaplan–Meier method, and factors associated with mortality were assessed through Cox proportional hazards regression analysis. The study population consisted of 226 patients, the majority of whom were male. The median survival time was 8.57 months (95% CI: 7.06–10.08), and survival rates declined markedly over the first five years. Significant differences in survival were observed across sex, age group, histological subtype, treatment status, treatment modality, and metastasis. Multivariable analysis demonstrated that male sex, age ≥ 80 years, small cell carcinoma, distant metastasis, and absence of treatment independently increased the risk of mortality. The findings indicate that survival among elderly lung cancer patients is notably low and that clinical and demographic characteristics play a major role in determining prognosis. Enhancing early diagnosis, improving access to treatment, and optimizing care pathways particularly for the oldest age groups and those with metastatic disease may contribute to reducing mortality in this vulnerable population.

INTRODUCTION

Advancing age is the most important risk factor for cancer in general and for many individual cancer types. Cancer incidence increases progressively with age, with a marked rise after midlife and exceeding 1,000 per 100,000 individuals after the age of 60¹. Approximately 60% of all cancer cases and 70% of cancer-related deaths occur in individuals aged 65 years and older². According to Globocan 2022 data, lung cancer is the most frequently diagnosed malignancy in the elderly population, both in Turkey and worldwide. Over the past three decades, the incidence of lung cancer has steadily increased, making it the leading cause of cancer-related mortality globally. As reported in the Globocan 2022 data, lung cancer ranks first in both incidence and cancer-related deaths across both sexes worldwide. It accounts for 12.4% (2,480,308 cases) of all cancer diagnoses and 18.7% (1,817,131 deaths) of cancer-related mortality³. In Europe, lung cancer ranks third in incidence among individuals aged 65 years and older, following colorectal and prostate cancers, and first in mortality. In the United States, it ranks sixth in incidence in the same age group, following prostate, breast, colorectal, stomach, and liver cancers, but ranks third in mortality, after prostate and liver cancers⁴. In Asia, including Turkey, lung cancer has the highest incidence and mortality among the elderly population⁵.

This study aimed to evaluate five-year overall survival and associated prognostic factors in elderly patients diagnosed with lung cancer.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The study population of this retrospective cohort study consisted of lung cancer cases aged 65 years and older, obtained from the Sivas Provincial Directorate of Health, with a completed five-year follow-up period from the date of diagnosis. To ensure the completion of the follow-up, patients residing in Sivas province and diagnosed with lung cancer between 2013 and 2017 were included. Data for patients diagnosed in 2013 were followed until the end of 2018, and for those

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diagnosed in 2017, follow-up continued until the end of 2022. The dependent variable was five-year survival rates were calculated for patients diagnosed during the 2013–2017 period. Independent variables included sociodemographic characteristics and disease-related factors.

Sivas province serves as a regional referral center for health care services in central Anatolia. Secondary and tertiary health care for cancer patients is primarily provided by Sivas Cumhuriyet University Hospital and state hospitals affiliated with the Ministry of Health. These institutions offer comprehensive oncological services, including diagnostic imaging, pathology, surgical oncology, medical oncology, radiotherapy, and palliative care. During the study period, lung cancer diagnosis, treatment, and follow-up were conducted within this integrated health care system, allowing for standardized management and reliable long-term follow-up of patients residing in the province.

Sample size calculation was based on survival rates reported in the literature for lung cancer patients⁶. To detect a 15% difference in survival rates between genders, a minimum sample size for two groups was calculated using the OpenEpi program with 80% power and a 5% significance level⁷. The calculation indicated that approximately 97 patients per group (a total of 194 patients) were required. In our study, analyses were conducted with a total of 226 patients.

A total of 255 patients diagnosed with lung cancer between 2013 and 2017 were retrieved from the database. Among these, 8 patients with invalid records and 12 patients residing outside Sivas were deemed ineligible and excluded. Consequently, 235 patients were initially evaluated. During the evaluation process, 3 patients with incomplete data and 5 patients who migrated from Sivas were further excluded. Ultimately, 227 patients with complete data and a minimum follow-up period of five years were included in the final analysis.

Sociodemographic variables comprised patient age (grouped as “young elderly” for 65–79 years and “very old” for 80 years and above), gender, place of birth (Sivas vs. non-Sivas), health insurance status (categorized as Social Institution + private + overseas vs. green card holders), place of residence (city center, district, village), and the socioeconomic development level of the districts they lived in. The

socioeconomic development level was determined using the Socioeconomic Development Ranking Research Report (SEGE-2017) prepared by the Republic of Turkey Ministry of Industry and Technology⁸. In this report, districts are ranked from 1 to 6 according to their level of development, with category 1 representing the most developed districts and category 6 the least developed. Districts within Sivas province fall into categories 2, 3, 4, and 5.

Disease-related variables included year of diagnosis (2013, 2014, 2015, 2016, 2017), histological type (adenocarcinoma, small cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and others such as malignant neoplasia), metastasis status (none, regional, distant, unknown), differentiation grade (well, moderate, poor, other, unknown), tumor sequence number (single primary, multiple primary), number of comorbidities (0, 1, 2 or more, unknown), and treatment status categorized as surgery, other treatments (chemotherapy, radiotherapy, immunotherapy, hormone therapy), both surgery and other treatments, no treatment, and unknown.

Descriptive analyses were conducted to characterize the study population. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard error (SE) or median with minimum and maximum values, depending on their distribution. Categorical variables were summarized using absolute (n) and relative (%) frequencies.

Kaplan–Meier analysis was used to estimate survival over different time periods, and the log-rank test was employed to compare survival distributions across independent variables. Multivariate analysis was conducted using Cox proportional hazards regression, with hazard ratios (HR) reported along with 95% confidence intervals. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Data analysis was performed using the SPSS-22 statistical software package (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). Univariate analyses were initially carried out to examine the association between each independent variable and overall survival. Kaplan–Meier survival curves were generated, and the log-rank test was used to compare survival distributions across categorical groups, including sex, age group (65–79 vs. ≥ 80), histological subtype, metastasis status, treatment status, and treatment modality.

Permission was obtained for this study from the Sivas Cumhuriyet University Non-Interventional Clinical Research Ethics Committee (18.01.2023-2023/01/08). The study was conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, as revised in 2013. This manuscript is based on and derived from the doctoral dissertation of the first author.

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the patients

	Overall	Survival time	
		< 5 year	≥5 year
Total participants (n)	226	193	33
Mean (SD) age(years)	72.2±5.5	72.3 (5.6)	71.9 (5.4)
Male [n (%)]	191 (84.5)	169 (87.6)	22 (66.7)
Female	35 (15.5)	24 (12.4)	11 (33.3)
Age			
65-79	196 (86.7)	166 (86.0)	30 (90.9)
80 and above	30 (13.3)	27 (14.0)	3 (9.1)
Place of birth			
Sivas [n (%)]	213 (94.2)	180 (93.3)	33 (100.0)
Other [n (%)]	13 (5.8)	13 (6.7)	0.00
Place of residence [n (%)]			
Center	119 (52.7)	98 (50.7)	21 (63.7)
District	52 (23.0)	48 (24.9)	4 (12.1)
Village	55 (24.3)	47 (24.3)	8 (24.2)
District category (SEGE 2017) [n (%)]			
Category 2	101 (52.3)	93 (48.2)	21 (63.6)
Category 3-4	50 (25.9)	49 (25.4)	8 (24.2)
Category 5	42 (21.8)	51 (26.4)	4 (12.1)
Health Assurance [n (%)]			
Green Card*	25 (11.1)	21 (10.9)	4 (12.1)
SGK+other	201 (88.9)	172 (89.1)	29 (87.9)
Years of Diagnosis [n(%)]			
2013	46 (20.4)	37 (19.2)	9 (27.3)
2014	51 (22.6)	47 (24.4)	4 (12.1)
2015	62 (27.4)	53 (27.5)	9 (27.3)
2016	33 (14.6)	29 (15.0)	4 (12.1)
2017	34 (15.0)	27 (14.0)	7 (21.2)

* Green card: It is a card given by the state to those whose economic status is below 1/3 of the minimum wage. The patient benefits from public hospitals free of charge Other: private insurance and overseas insurance. SGK: Social Security Institution

Histologically, 33.2% (n=75) of patients had squamous cell carcinoma, while 50.9% received non-surgical treatments (chemotherapy, radiotherapy, immunotherapy, hormone therapy). Both surgery and other treatment modalities were present in 84.9% (n=192) of the patients. Among the 204 patients with available treatment information, 77.9% (n=159) received treatment. Surgery was performed in 41.5% of (Table 2).

Table 2. Clinical characteristics of the patients

	Survival Time		
	Overall (n=226) n (%)	<5 yil (n=193) n (%)	≥5 yil (n=33) n (%)
Histological Type			
Adenocarcinoma	66 (29.2)	51 (26.4)	15 (45.4)
Squamous Cell Carcinoma	75 (33.2)	63 (32.6)	12 (36.4)
Small Cell Carcinoma	60 (26.6)	57 (29.6)	3 (9.1)
Other	25 (11.0)	22 (11.4)	3 (9.1)
Treatment status			
Yes	159 (70.3)	132 (68.4)	27 (81.8)
No	45 (19.9)	44 (22.8)	1 (3.1)
Unknown	22 (9.8)	77 (39.8)	5 (15.1)
Treatment type *			
Surgical	66 (41.5)	56 (42.4)	10 (37.0)
Other	81 (50.9)	71 (53.8)	10 (37.0)
Surgery+other	12 (7.5)	5 (3.8)	7 (26.0)
Number of chronic disease			
No	16 (7.1)	13 (6.7)	3 (9.1)
One	104 (46.0)	88 (45.6)	16 (48.5)
2 and above	88 (38.9)	75 (38.9)	13 (39.4)
Unknown	18 (8.0)	17 (8.8)	1 (3.0)
Number of Tumors			
Single tumor	216 (95.6)	184 (95.3)	32 (97.0)
Multiple tumors	10 (4.4)	9 (4.7)	1 (3.0)
Metastasis			
No	90 (39.8)	57 (29.6)	33 (100.0)
Yes	136 (60.2)	136 (70.4)	0 (0.0)

* Among those receiving treatment

The mortality rates were 58.0% (n=131) at one year, 82.7% survival times in women were 18 and 27 months, respectively. (n=187) at three years, and 85.4% (n=193) at five years post- In men, 38.2% survived one year, decreasing significantly to diagnosis. Median survival time was 8.57 ± 0.77 months (95% 14.7% at three years, and only 11.5% reached five-year CI: 7.06–10.08), and mean survival time was 17.53 ± 1.34 survival. Median and mean survival times in men were 8.11 ± months (95% CI: 14.90–20.16). Among women, 62.9% 1.13 months (95% CI: 5.89–10.34) and 15.78 ± 1.36 months survived at least one year, decreasing to 31.4% at three years (95% CI: 13.10–18.46), respectively (Table 3). and remaining at 31.4% at five years. Median and mean

Table 3. Five-Year Survival Rates and Duration by Gender in Elderly Lung Cancer Patients

Survival Rate (n=226)	Total		Female		Male	
	n	%	n	%	n	%
One-year survival	95	42.0	22	62.9	73	38.2
Three-year survival	39	17.3	11	31.4	28	14.7
Five-year survival	33	14.6	11	31.4	22	11.5
	Mean ± Standard Error (95% CI)		Mean ± Standard Error (95% CI)		Mean ± Standard Error (95% CI)	
Five-year survival duration (months)	17.53±1.34 (14.90-20.16)		27.05±4.03 (19.15-34.95)		15.78±1.36 (13.10-18.46)	
	Median ± Standard Error (95% CI)		Median ± Standard Error (95% CI)		Median ± Standard Error (95% CI)	
Five-year survival duration (months)	8.57±0.77 (7.06-10.08)		18.53±4.97 (8.78-28.27)		8.11±1.13 (5.89-10.34)	

CI: Confidence Intervals

Five-year survival analysis using Kaplan–Meier estimates and log-rank tests identified several groups with significantly poorer survival outcomes. These included males, with a median survival of 3.6 months ($p < 0.001$); patients aged 80 years and older, with a median survival of 3.3 months ($p = 0.019$); patients diagnosed with small cell carcinoma, whose median survival was 6.2 months ($p < 0.001$); patients with metastasis at diagnosis, with a median survival of 4.3 months ($p < 0.001$); and patients who did not receive treatment, having a median survival of 3.6 months ($p < 0.001$). In addition, the median survival time of patients whose treatment was unknown was significantly reduced by 17.4 months ($p = 0.008$) (Table 4- Figure 1).

Figure 1. Kaplan–Meier Survival by Gender in Elderly Lung Cancer Patients

Multivariate Cox regression analysis revealed that male patients had a 1.60-fold increased risk of mortality compared to females ($p = 0.037$). Patients aged 80 years and older had a 1.85-fold higher mortality risk compared to younger patients ($p = 0.004$). Those diagnosed with small cell carcinoma had a 1.53-fold increased mortality risk relative to patients with adenocarcinoma ($p = 0.031$). Presence of metastasis was associated with a 5.35-fold higher risk of death ($p < 0.001$). Although patients who did not receive treatment had a 1.27-fold higher risk of mortality compared to those who received treatment, this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.194$) (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

In this study, we analyzed the five-year survival of elderly patients with lung cancer and the factors influencing it. It was found that the median survival time was 8.5 months, with shorter survival times in men, patients aged 80 and above, those with small cell carcinoma, those not receiving treatment, and those with metastasis.

In this study, the mean age of the patients was found to be 72.2 years. The mean age (72.4) was similar to Akin M's study conducted on elderly patients presenting to the outpatient clinic⁹. In a study conducted by Brown JS et al. in the United Kingdom, which is similar to this study, all lung cancer cases were screened within 30 months and the mean age was found to be 71 years¹⁰. In another study conducted by Rao et al. in the USA to investigate lung cancers in the elderly, the median age was found to be 70¹¹. In a study conducted by Zhang Q et al. to investigate lung cancers in the USA between 2010 and 2015, approximately half of the patients were between 61 and 75 years of age¹².

In the study, 84.5% of the elderly lung cancer patients were male. Similar to this study, nine out of ten patients with lung cancer were male in a previous study conducted by Taş F et al. at Istanbul University including elderly patients¹³. Again, in a study conducted by Akin M in elderly patients with lung cancer admitted to a radiation oncology outpatient clinic, it was reported that 93.8% of the patients were male⁹. This finding obtained in this study is consistent with the literature. According to Globocan 2022 data, lung cancer, which is most common in men in Turkey, has the highest rate in the world³.

Table 4. Five-year survival rates and median survival times according to socio-demographic and clinical characteristics (Kaplan–Meier analysis)

N= 226	Five-year survival rate (%)	Median survival(months) ±SE (95% CI)	P (log rank)
Gender			
Male	11.5	8.1± 1.1 (8.7-28.2)	0.005
Female	31.4	18.5±4.9 (5.8-10.3)	
Age			
65-79	15.3	9.8±1.3(7.2-12.4)	0.019
80 and above	10.0	3.3±1.2 (0.8-5.8)	
Place of residence			
Center	17.6	9.79±1.6 (6.4-13.1)	0.128
District-village	11.2	8.27±1.4 (5.3±11.1)	
District category (SEGE 2017)			
Category 2	17.2	9.79±1.5(6.7-12.9)	0.159
Category 3-4-5	11.5	8.14±1.4(5.3-10.9)	
Health Assurance [n (%)]			
Green Card*	16.0	8.7±2.8(3.0-14.3)	0.845
SGK+Paid and insured from abroad	14.4	8.5±0.93(6.6-10.3)	
Histological Type			
Adenocarcinoma (n=66)	22.7	15.7±2.4(10.9-20.5)	<0.001
Squamous Cell Carcinoma (n=75)	16.0	8.5±1.9(4.6-12.4)	
Small Cell Carcinoma (n=60)	5.0	6.2±2.7(0.7-11.7)	
Other (n=25)	12.0	4.3±1.7(0.9-7.8)	
Treatment status			
Yes (n=159)	17.0	10.0±1.4(7.2-12.8)	<0.001
No (n=45)	2.2	3.6±0.5(2.4-4.8)	
Unknown (n=22)	22.7	11.2±2.3(6.5-15.8)	
Treatment type		(Mean±CI)	0.008
Surgical (n=66)	15.2	17.5±2.5(12.5-22.5)	
Other (n=81)	12.3	17.4±2.0(13.3-21.5)	
Surgery+other (n=12)	58.3	39.8±7.1(25.7-53.8)	
Unknown (n=67)	9.0	13.6±2.1(9.3-17.8)	
Number of comorbid diseases			
No (n=16)	18.9	8.2±6.6(0.0-21.3)	0.771
One (n=104)	15.4	9.8±1.7(6.3-13.2)	
2 and above (n=88)	14.8	7.5±1.5(4.5-10.6)	
Unknown (n=18)	5	9.7±4.9(0.0-19.4)	
Number of Tumors			
Single tumor (n=216)	14.8	8.2±1.0(6.2-10.3)	0.586
Multiple tumors (n=10)	10.0	15.9±0.72(7.0-10.0)	
Metastasis			
No	36.7	27.5±05.39 (17.0-38.1)	<0.001
Yes	0.0	4.3±0.6 (3.0-5.7)	

Green card: It is a card given by the state to those whose economic status is below 1/3 of the minimum wage. The patient benefits from public hospitals free of charge, SGK: Social Security Institute, SE: Standard error, CI: Confidence Intervals

Table 5. Association between survival time and variables

Variable	Survival time of 5 years	
	Hazard Ratio (95% CI)	P Value
Male		
Female	1.00 (reference)	
Male	1.60 (1.03- 2.49)	0.037
Age		
65-79	1.00 (reference)	
80 and above	1.85 (1.21-2.84)	0.004
Histological Type		
Adenocarcinoma	1.17 (0.83-1.71)	0.412
Squamous Cell Carcinoma	1.53 (1.04-2.27)	0.031
Small Cell Carcinoma	1.52 (0.90-2.57)	0.116
Other	1.00 (reference)	
Treatment status		
Yes	1.27 (0.88-1.82)	0.194
No	(reference)	
Metastasis		
No	5.35(3.69-7.74)	<0.001
Yes		

CI: Confidence Intervals

In this study, the most common types of lung cancer were found to be, squamous cell carcinoma, adenocarcinoma and small cell carcinoma, in order of frequency. In the study conducted by Arslan et al., it was reported that squamous cell carcinoma was more common in the elderly in Sivas province¹⁴. Venuta et al. reported in their study that squamous cell carcinoma increased after the age of 65 and reached 38% after the age of 75¹⁵. Similarly, adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma were found to be the most common types in a study conducted by Wisnivesky et al. in the USA between 1990 and 1999, in which the gender differences of lung cancers were examined¹⁶. Zhang found adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and small cell carcinoma as the most common types, respectively¹². Taş found adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and small cell carcinoma as the most common types in his study¹³. The World Health Organization also states that adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and small cell carcinoma are the most dominant types of lung cancer¹⁷. The differences in the most common cancer types between this study and other studies are generally dependent on the age group of the patients included in the study.

One-year survival rate in elderly lung cancer patients was found to be 42.0% in this study. Taş found a similar one-year survival rate of 42.5% in the elderly¹³. In a study by Söğüt G, the one-year survival rate was 53.1% in lung cancer patients

including the elderly (mean age 59.4 years) diagnosed in the chest diseases clinic of a university¹⁸. This higher rate may be explained by the fact that the study was performed in younger patients. A similar result was observed in a study conducted by Abedi S et al. in Iran with 102 lung cancer patients (mean age of 63 years) and this rate was found to be 57%¹⁹. Despite the younger patient group, lower survival rates are also observed; the level of development of the countries where the studies were conducted as well as the time of the study may play a role in this difference. In a study conducted by Lachgar et al. in Morocco to evaluate all-age group lung cancers seen between 2005 and 2008, the one-year survival rate was found to be lower at 31.7%²⁰.

In the study, 14.6% of the patients completed the 5-year survival period. Lachgar et al. found this rate to be 3.4% in their study²⁰. In a study by Owonikoko TK et al. covering the years 1988-2003 in the USA, it was found to be 12.3% in the age range of 70-79 years and 7.4% at the age of 80 years and above²¹. In a study conducted by Yung-Hung Luo et al. between 1997 and 2017 in patients aged 50-80 years with lung cancer who were smokers, the 5-year overall survival rate was around 20%²². The difference between these two studies may be due to the level of development of the countries. Abedi et al. found a 5-year survival rate of 13%, slightly lower than this study¹⁹. In the study conducted by Bing-Yen Wang et al. in

Taiwan with lung cancer patients diagnosed between 2002 and 2008, the 5-year survival rate for patients aged 65 years and older was slightly lower (12.6%); this difference may be because the patients in the study group were in an older period including the years 2002-2008²³.

The median survival time of the patients included in this study was found to be 8.5 months. Similarly, Owonikoko TK found a median 5-year survival time of 11.8 months in patients over 65 years of age²¹. Taş F found the median survival time as 9.4 months in his study¹³. Akın et al. found the median survival as 11.3 months in their study⁹. In the study conducted by Yang R et al. in the USA, in which the relationship between racial and socioeconomic status and lung cancers observed between 1998 and 2002 was examined, median survival was found to be 8.7 months²⁴. In the Yung-Hung Luo study, the median overall survival was found to be 16.9 months²².

When evaluated by gender, the 5-year median survival time was found to be shorter in men than in women (8.1, and 18.5 months, respectively). In a study conducted by Laerum D et al. on 1261 patients diagnosed with lung cancer between 2007 and 2016, similar to our study, it was reported that survival was significantly shorter in men than in women by 9 months; however, the significance disappeared after adjustment for clinical and biological factors. In the study, the difference between genders was explained by the higher number of early-stage cases in women and late-stage cases in men²⁵. Health-seeking behaviors between genders may also be a reason for the gender disparity in survival. In a systematic review of 42 studies on gender differences in health-seeking behaviors in lung cancer cases, differences in favor of women were determined²⁶. In a study conducted by Gedvialite V et al. in Lithuania, in which patients diagnosed with lung cancer between 2003 and 2012 were analyzed, it was reported that the survival time of women was longer than that of men²⁷. Bing-Yen Wang et al. similarly reported a median survival of 20.8 months in women and 10.7 months in men²³. Kristiansen C et al. reported that there was no significant difference between men and women in terms of 5-year survival in a study of lung cancers seen in Denmark between 1980 and 2012. This was reported to be due to the increase in smoking habits among women, especially in the 1970s²⁸.

This study found an overall five-year survival rate of 22.7% for adenocarcinomas, 16.0% for squamous cell carcinomas, and 5.0% for small cell lung cancers. In a study of lung cancer

patients in Qatar conducted by Abdel-Salam AG et al. between 2010 and 2014, the median survival time was 12.3 months for small cell carcinomas and 17.9 months for non-small cell carcinomas²⁹. Matthew B. Schabath et al. analyzed 1,032 cases of small cell lung cancer diagnosed between 1986 and 2008 and reported an 11% increase in the five-year survival rate³⁰. The higher five-year survival rate found in this study may be attributable to disparities in health care across countries and differences in smoking habits.

In this study, untreated lung cancer patients had significantly shorter survival times than treated patients (2.2 and 17.0 month, respectively). Survival duration also varies according to the type of treatment. In a study by Bing-Yen Wang et al. including elderly patients, 57.1% of patients who underwent surgery, 10.9% of those who received chemotherapy, and 7.9% of those who received radiotherapy completed the 5-year survival period²³. In this study, the rate of patients who completed 5-year survival using both surgery and other treatment modalities was 23.5%. This difference between the two studies may be due to the difference in the age distribution of the patients as well as the time of the study.

One of the main strengths of this study is that it is the only study in the region to examine lung cancer survival among the elderly using official institutional data. Comparing the survival outcomes of elderly lung cancer patients living in Sivas with both national and global data is significant for evaluating the provision and effectiveness of healthcare services in the region. However, the study has some limitations, including the lack of socioeconomic data and information on patients' smoking status.

CONCLUSIONS

The median survival time in elderly lung cancer patients is short, 8.5 months, and approximately nine out of ten patients die within five years. The risk of death is significantly higher in men and patients over 80 years of age, in patients with small cell types, in untreated patients, and in those with metastases. Socioeconomic information, clinicopathological data, and causes of death are needed to better analyze the factors affecting 5-year survival in elderly lung cancer patients. Therefore, cancer registries must be accurate, reliable, and comply with international standards.

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Data curation → SC, RU Formal analysis → SC, RU
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